

Novel Formula For Finding Densities Of Materials Using Only Length As A Parameter

Utkarsh Kumar

May 2026

Abstract

This paper presents the derivation of the following formula:

$$\rho_m = \rho_l \cdot \frac{h_s r_0^2 - h_l r_l^2}{h_0 r_0^2 - h_l r_l^2}$$

which allows us to measure the density of any material just using a liquid of known density of ρ_l and a cup of the given material using only length as a required parameter.

1 Introduction

Science is nothing but the
refinement of everyday thinking.

Albert Einstein

Measuring density is a task required across many fields, ranging from biology to geology to even archaeology. But the instruments required are heavy and need electricity, and it is not possible for all the resources to exist on hand. This formula, though requiring a vessel of the given material, still works even if there is a dent in the body — it still acts as a glass. Though the derivation assumes a perfect cylinder, further work could allow measurement across all shapes. The following formula was derived from the observation of a steel glass floating on water while having some water in it, which was analyzed using principles of hydrostatics to yield the formula.

2 Theory And Derivation

The following variables are defined as per Figure 1:

- h_0 — total outer height of the vessel
- h_l — total inner height of the vessel

- h_s — depth of the vessel submerged in the liquid
- h_l — height of liquid inside the vessel
- r_0 — outer radius of the vessel
- r_I — inner radius of the vessel
- ρ_m — density of the vessel material (to be determined)
- ρ_l — density of the reference liquid (known)
- g — gravitational acceleration constant

Figure 1: Cross-sectional view of the floating vessel setup showing all measured parameters

In this derivation we assume that there is no surface tension and the vessel is of uniform thickness.

2.1 Derivation

Mass of vessel:

$$M_m = (\pi h_0 r_0^2 - \pi h_l r_I^2) \rho_m$$

Mass of liquid inside vessel:

$$M_l = \pi h_l r_I^2 \rho_l$$

Weight of vessel including liquid inside it (W):

$$W = ((\pi h_0 r_0^2 - \pi h_l r_I^2) \rho_m + \pi h_l r_I^2 \rho_l) g$$

Buoyant force (F_b):

$$F_b = \pi h_s r_0^2 \rho_l g$$

For the vessel to float, $F_b = W$:

$$((\pi h_0 r_0^2 - \pi h_I r_I^2) \rho_m + \pi h_l r_I^2 \rho_l) g = \pi h_s r_0^2 \rho_l g$$

Canceling g from both sides:

$$((\pi h_0 r_0^2 - \pi h_I r_I^2) \rho_m + \pi h_l r_I^2 \rho_l) = \pi h_s r_0^2 \rho_l$$

Rearranging:

$$\begin{aligned} (\pi h_0 r_0^2 - \pi h_I r_I^2) \rho_m &= \pi h_s r_0^2 \rho_l - \pi h_l r_I^2 \rho_l \\ \rho_m &= \frac{\pi \rho_l (h_s r_0^2 - h_l r_I^2)}{\pi (h_0 r_0^2 - h_I r_I^2)} \end{aligned}$$

Canceling π from numerator and denominator:

$$\boxed{\rho_m = \rho_l \cdot \frac{h_s r_0^2 - h_l r_I^2}{h_0 r_0^2 - h_I r_I^2}}$$

It is notable that the denominator represents the volume of the vessel material and the numerator represents the net volume of liquid displaced, giving the formula a clear geometric interpretation.

3 Experimental Verification

Here we verify the formula by doing the following experiment: Material required: ruler or any length measuring device, cup of given material (steel in our case), liquid with known density (water in our case). the following measurements were taken:

- $h_0 = 96.6$ mm — total outer height of vessel
- $h_I = 95.1$ mm — total inner height of vessel
- $h_s = 95.1$ mm — depth of vessel submerged
- $h_l = 63.1$ mm — height of liquid inside vessel
- $r_0 = 32.8$ mm — outer radius
- $r_I = 32.3$ mm — inner radius
- $\rho_l = 1000$ kg/m³ — density of water

Substituting into the formula:

$$\rho_m = 1000 \cdot \frac{(95.1)(32.8)^2 - (63.1)(32.3)^2}{(96.6)(32.8)^2 - (95.1)(32.3)^2}$$

Evaluating the numerator:

$$(95.1)(32.8)^2 - (63.1)(32.3)^2 = 102312.384 - 65831.599 = 36480.785 \text{ mm}^3$$

Evaluating the denominator:

$$(96.6)(32.8)^2 - (95.1)(32.3)^2 = 103926.144 - 99216.879 = 4709.265 \text{ mm}^3$$

Therefore:

$$\rho_m = 1000 \cdot \frac{36480.785}{4709.265} = 7747.4 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

The accepted density of steel ranges from 7750 to 8050 kg/m³. The calculated value of 7747.4 kg/m³ differs from the lower bound by only 2.6 kg/m³, corresponding to a percentage error of 0.03%.

4 Discussion

4.1 Source of error

- The used vessel had chamfer at the base.
- Surface tension can play a slight role in the movement when $h_s \approx h_o$
- The vessel had a design that slightly reduced the volume.

4.2 Limitations

The following method has some limitations such as: This can't be used on all shapes, the error can increase with slight differences in observed volume

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a novel method for determining the density of a material using only length measurements and a liquid of known density. By analyzing the hydrostatic equilibrium of a hollow cylindrical vessel floating in a liquid, the following formula was derived:

$$\rho_m = \rho_l \cdot \frac{h_s r_0^2 - h_l r_I^2}{h_o r_0^2 - h_I r_I^2}$$

The formula was validated experimentally using a steel vessel floating in water, yielding a density of 7747.4 kg/m³, which is within 0.03% of the accepted value. The method requires no weighing scale, no electricity, and no complex laboratory equipment — only a ruler and a liquid of known density. It is notable that the denominator of the formula represents the volume of the vessel material and the numerator represents the net volume of liquid displaced, giving the formula a clear geometric interpretation rooted in Archimedes' principle. Further work could extend this method to vessels of non-uniform cross-section, broadening its applicability.

References

1. Archimedes, *On Floating Bodies*, c. 250 BC.
2. Young, H. D., Freedman, R. A., *University Physics with Modern Physics*, 14th ed. Pearson, 2015.
3. Engineering Toolbox, “Density of Steel,” *engineeringtoolbox.com*, 2004. Available: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/steel-density-d_1999.html